

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa - CINECA -

Deliverable D4.2 - Framework and APIs for executing federated genomics analyses

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1. Executive Summary

The main scope of this deliverable is to gather technical requirements and frameworks for a federated analysis platform. In task 4.3 “Federated Genomic Analyses Algorithm Development”, the project partners have described the following use cases:

- 4.3.1. Federated joint cohort genotyping;
- 4.3.2. Polygenic Risk Scores (PRS) workflow across two similar ethnic background sample sets;
- 4.3.3. Federated QTL analysis for molecular phenotypes.

The federated analysis platform defined by this task aims to provide technological solutions for these use cases. In this deliverable, we gathered the technical requirements based on these use case descriptions and wrote a short design document which explains the requirements and lists the different options for a solution. These requirements were gathered by conducting a short survey among the CINECA WP4 partners covered in the aforementioned document (4.3 “Federated Genomic Analyses Algorithm Development”), in order to better understand their use cases and offer solutions to cover them.

Three distinct frameworks were considered to address the requirements from the use-cases. The chosen framework supports different computing environments, which is a requirement for true federated analysis. The framework also supports extending compatibility with GA4GH standards, such as WES, htsget, and AAI / Passports. Plans to extend this proposed solution beyond these initial sites will be carried out after the initial phase of validation. One of the objectives is to propose solutions that will be useful for an audience of sites beyond the ones in the survey. This can be checked directly by discussing the chosen solutions with WP5 - Healthcare Interoperability and Clinical Applications - to see if it could be integrated into a WP5 use case.

2. Project Objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached the following project objectives:

- a) Understanding the data sources and data types needed for cross-cohort analysis applications. By using a diverse set of institutions a wide picture was obtained.
- b) Identified the data ingestion workflows, specifically which interfaces and protocols are used for transferring data. Several ones were identified, see Table 1 and Figure 1.
- c) Ascertained the authentication and authorisation methods used to access the data. Each of the data interfaces has its own authentication mechanism that needs to be bridged with the ELIXIR AAI.
- d) Designed several potential deployment scenarios which could satisfy the needs of the use cases.

3. Detailed Report on the Deliverable

3.1. Background

As a starting point for this deliverable, a data workflow survey was conducted among work package partners in the summer of 2019. Appendix 7.1 “Data Workflow Survey” lists the questions and all answers received. A total of 6 work package partners participated in this survey:

- HES-SO & SIB, Switzerland
- University of Tartu, Estonia
- University Medical Center Groningen (BIOS), Netherlands
- University of Oxford, UK
- University of Cape Town, South Africa
- EGA group, EMBL-EBI, UK

The survey demonstrated that the data sources needed for the analysis vary a great deal between sites. According to the survey results, there are four big data storage archives which are used the most frequently for accessing the data:

Table 1. Data workflow survey summary

Parameters	Parameters
Data types	Genome sequences (whole genomes, exomes, chip data), phenotypic data (demographics, disease status, medication), metadata, other data types (documents, presentations, images)
File formats	Data: CRAM, BAM/SAM, FASTQ, VCF, TSV, CSV, Tabix indexes Metadata: DATS/DataMed, DCAT, XML, TSV
Data storage	Controlled access: EGA, dbGap Open access: ENA, GEO
Transfer protocol	Manual: http(s), (s)ftp, Globus, Aspera Automated: htsgget
Access rights	Per-user basis (no external access), token based (ELIXIR AAI, Switch AAI)

In addition, there are similarities in the overall architecture of computing environments used for the analysis:

Figure 1. Data workflow

Usually the data is fetched from the data storage and placed in an internal storage system, which is then accessed by the computing cluster nodes. It is very rare to stream the data directly from the data storage archive, e.g. using the htsget¹ streaming protocol. In most cases data transfer happens using traditional transfer protocols like http(s) or (s)ftp. Also, there is a high degree of variance in both the data and the file types, which limits the transfer protocols to traditional ones. Data types include primarily genome sequences and phenotype data, but also other data types ranging from presentation files to text documents.

3.2. Proposed Framework and APIs

After discussing the survey results between CINECA WP4 partners, it was decided that any solution should use APIs compatible with GA4GH² cloud API standards as much as possible. GA4GH Cloud Web Services currently has four API standards:

- **TRS** for sharing of tools and workflows;
- **TES** for executing individual jobs on computing platforms using a standard API;
- **WES** for running full workflows on execution platforms;
- **DRS** to read and write data objects across clouds in an agnostic way.

These API standards are inspired by large-scale distributed computing projects. Figure 2 depicts a typical functional architecture of a computing ecosystem proposed by GA4GH Cloud Web Services. The four GA4GH cloud services are intended to be independent of each other, thus each cloud web

¹ <http://samtools.github.io/hts-specs/htsget.html>

² <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

service can be deployed in an independent cloud provider (private or public). Due to the fact that in general the data processed is sensitive, these services are deployed only in the private clouds managed by the different sites.

Figure 2. GA4GH compatible cloud platform (functional architecture)

3.3. Deployment Scenarios for Federated Genomics Analysis

The following three deployment scenarios were discussed for federated genomics analysis cloud APIs.

3.3.1. CWL and GA4GH compatible ELIXIR Cloud APIs

Under this deployment scenario, the WES (CWL-WES³) and TES (TESK⁴) services being developed by ELIXIR Cloud⁵ project can be deployed on one or more site infrastructure, such as a private or public cloud. As each of the logical blocks (TRS, WES, TES, DRS) is meant to be deployed independently and communicate using GA4GH APIs, the architecture design does not impose any restriction. For data access, it is assumed data is made available to the data staging area within the cluster. Figure 3 depicts this deployment model in which a single centralised WES and federated TES endpoints are deployed. Each federated TES is equal to the rest. The authentication is managed by Elixir AAI⁶. The client that sends the workflow to CWL-WES will obtain a TOKEN from Elixir AAI and attach it to the request together with the workflow. WES-ELIXIR will distribute tasks to the TESK and collect the results.

³ <https://github.com/elixir-cloud-aai/cwl-WES>

⁴ <https://github.com/EMBL-FBI-TSI/TESK>

⁵ <https://elixir-europe.github.io/cloud/>

⁶ <https://elixir-europe.org/services/compute/aai>

Figure 3. Deployment scenario 1

Deployment of APIs in this scenario have the following dependencies:

- **Docker and Kubernetes:** WES and TES services from ELIXIR Cloud and AAI project only support Docker and Kubernetes runtime environments.
- **CWL Workflows:** Elixir Cloud and AAI APIs currently only support CWL workflow execution.

3.3.2. Nextflow and GA4GH Compatible Services (WES and TES)

This deployment scenario replaces CWL-WES with Nextflow⁷, a widely used workflow language and executor service. By adding a WES shim and making it compatible with GA4GH, it would be possible to execute existing Nextflow workflows using a WES client. One option for a WES shim is Nextflow Tower⁸. The executor in this scenario is TESK⁹ which acts as a TES endpoint. Nextflow and TESK will communicate using the standard GA4GH API. For data access, it is assumed the data is made available to the data staging area within at least one of the clusters, for example by using a shared volume or a central file server from where the data is then copied to where it is needed for analysis. Figure 4 depicts this deployment model where a centralised WES (Nextflow manager) and federated TES (TESK) endpoints are deployed in several CINECA WP4 partners. TESK authentication is managed by Elixir AAI. At the moment Nextflow Tower does not directly support Elixir AAI, but it would be possible to configure it using OAuth¹⁰.

⁷ <https://www.nextflow.io/>

⁸ <https://tower.nf/>

⁹ <https://github.com/EMBL-EBI-TSI/TESK>

¹⁰ <https://oauth.net/>

Figure 4. Deployment scenario 2

Deployment of APIs in this scenario have the following dependencies:

- **Kubernetes:** TESK currently only supports Kubernetes runtime environments. The other components do not require Kubernetes, but may be deployed using docker.
- **Nextflow Workflows:** Nextflow manager supports only execution of Nextflow workflows.
- **Nextflow Tower:** It is planned¹¹ by Nextflow developers to add support to a WES compatibility layer.. So even though this is currently not implemented in Nextflow Tower, it is the most promising way to implement a WES shim.

3.3.3. Nextflow With Multiple Executors and an Optional Tes Layer

Scenarios 1 and 2 are disadvantaged by the fact that they either require all cohorts participating in a cross-cohort analysis to support a specific set of services, or rely on functionality not yet implemented (such as WES support in Nextflow Tower). In light of this, this scenario was developed to allow for flexibility and for a practical implementation.

Under this scenario, sites deploy a Nextflow manager which replaces WES as a workflow to task mapping layer. The Nextflow executors in this scenario could be different computing environments, for example SLURM, SGE, Kubernetes, etc. These are computing environments commonly deployed at partner sites. For data access, it is assumed data is made available to the data staging area within the cluster.

In this deployment scenario, the executor environment is not required to be fully compatible with GA4GH TES/WES specifications. However, by allowing different execution services to be used, this scenario adds a lot of flexibility and provides a good transition mechanism to future, more fully

¹¹ <https://github.com/nextflow-io/nextflow/issues/1272>

GA4GH compliant environments. This scenario reduces the deployment and maintenance costs, since an already deployed execution service can be reused and because the computing resources are not being partitioned. Figure 5 depicts this deployment model where a centralised WES (Nextflow manager) is deployed in a cloud and multiple Nextflow executor endpoints are deployed by CINECA WP4 partners, each of these endpoints are designed to create tasks in their corresponding executors. This scenario does not contemplate a common authentication solution like Elixir AAI. Each partner must have an authentication solution for their resources.

This scenario offers two gradual ways of incorporating GA4GH Cloud standards:

- When we started work on this Work Package, Nextflow already had an incomplete, beta stage support for TES as an execution endpoint. By submitting a series of pull requests (#1589, #1664, #1666, #1696) we managed to make this component much more robust and verified that it can run the workflows of real life complexity levels.

Nextflow Tower, which is an orchestration level on top of Nextflow, has plans for supporting WES. This would eliminate the need for direct Nextflow to TES interaction and bring this closer to development scenario 2 described above. This work has not been started yet, but is planned for the future.

Figure 5. Deployment scenario 3

Deployment of APIs in this scenario have the following dependencies:

- **Specific Computing Environments:** Specific computing environments supported¹² by Nextflow executors could be used (Local, Grid Engine¹³, LSF, SLURM¹⁴, HTCondor¹⁵, Kubernetes, and more)

¹² <https://www.nextflow.io/docs/latest/executor.html>

¹³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Oracle_Grid_Engine

¹⁴ <https://slurm.schedmd.com/>

¹⁵ <https://research.cs.wisc.edu/htcondor/>

- **Nextflow Workflows:** Nextflow manager supports only execution of Nextflow workflows.

3.4. Proof of Concept Development and User story

Based on the considerations described above, Nextflow has been identified as a common technology denominator among the CINECA WP4 partners, and the PoC pipelines in Task 4.3 (PRS and QTL) will be developed using the **Deployment Scenario 3**. To ease the development efforts, a data staging area for the workflows would be implemented via a virtual cohort running at CSC's¹⁶ cPouta cloud¹⁷. Table 2 lists the services which are being developed and deployed as per this PoC.

Table 2. PoC development details

Endpoint	Technology	Deployment Details
Workflow manager 1	Nextflow Manager	Deployed at CSC's Rahti private cloud
TES 1	TESK	Deployed at CSC's Rahti private cloud
TES 2	TESK	Deployed at EMBL-EBI
Workflow manager 2	Nextflow Manager	Deployed at UTartu's private cloud
TES 3	Slurm	Deployed at UTartu's private cloud
Virtual Cohort provider	Federated EGA	Deployed at CSC's cPouta cloud

3.4.1. Federated Genomic Analysis User Story

This describes a general overview of a federated genomic analysis workflow.

Under the proposed approach, the analysis pipeline for each use case is split into two parts: part A runs on the private, individual level data in the cohort-specific environments; it produces summary-level products which are collected in a central location; and then part B aggregates the summary-level products into the final scientific product (see Figure 6).

¹⁶ <https://csc.fi/en/csc>

¹⁷ <https://research.csc.fi/-/cpouta>

Figure 6. General design for federated analysis pipelines

Under this approach and the Deployment Scenario 3, the analysis runs as follows:

- Part A of the pipeline is run in the environments of all appropriate cohorts and reduces private, individual level data to summary level products. The Nextflow manager delegates processes to the corresponding TES endpoints, and the analysis is executed on the corresponding TES endpoints.
- The results of the analysis from different TES endpoints are then aggregated at a central location.
- Part B of the pipeline collects the summary level products into the final scientific product, which is made available to the end user.

Data Transfer

Because a cohort does not maintain its own data analysis compute environment, the data of interest must be transferred from the cohort to the cloud compute environment where the federated analysis will be performed. Additionally, the user must be authenticated to determine if the user has access to these data. In developing these frameworks consideration has been given to the data transfer protocols and AAI standards (WP2) to ensure efficient access methods and handover from discovery (WP1). As not all cohorts support GA4GH Passports or htsget at this time, the framework runs on Data Staging Areas where data is staged for analysis, but the analyses will support htsget where this is supported.

Below we describe data access for different repositories of genetic and phenotypic data.

dbGap: Data Access Workflow

Prerequisites: The SRA toolkit should be installed in a location with read and write access to the Data Staging Area, the User must have access to the access controlled data and have access to its dbGAP repository key in the Data staging area.

1. Start the SRA toolkit and review its configuration. Import your dbGAP repository key in the SRA toolkit and authenticate the client with dbGAP. In the context of a computing analysis environment, the key storage is as sensitive as the data it opens access to. There must be a clear trust between the owner of the key and the compute environment, not only in the storage of the key, but also its transport and disposal. The SRA toolkit must temporarily store the key in a secure location, both parties must clearly agree on the specific measures needed and all the pertinent laws must be followed. Similarly the transport of the key must be performed alongside the workflow in a secure way. The security measures can be, but are not limited to, TLS or GPG encryption for transport of the key, encrypted filesystem, workflow isolation, etc
2. dbGAP authenticates the requested access.
3. Navigate the file you want to import, select the download location on staging area and confirm the import of the file.
4. SRA toolkit starts the file download, only if file access is allowed as per the role-based access control (RBAC) policy.
5. The downloaded file in step 5 is encrypted. The SRA toolkit's 'vdb-decrypt' utility can be used to decrypt the data.
6. The decrypted file is now available in the Data Staging Area.

When the analysis is finished, the resulting data will likely be needed to be transferred to the original data repository. The reintegration process is basically the opposite as the download process.

1. The data is available in the the Data Staging Area.
2. SRA toolkit data encrypts the data.
3. Start the SRA toolkit and review its configuration. Import your dbGAP repository key in the SRA toolkit and authenticate the client with dbGAP.
4. dbGAP authenticates the requested access.
5. Encrypted data is transferred using FTP to dbGAP, only if the RBAC policy allows to write files.

EGA: Data Access Workflow

The EGA maintains a htsgrep compatible Data API which is accessible to authenticated users. Additionally the EGA supports a python (pyega3¹⁸) command line client that delivers unencrypted data to the users, and a FUSE¹⁹ layer which virtually mounts the data in the users workspace facilitating direct access to the data.

Prerequisites: The user must have a valid EGA account with access to the data of interest. The user may also link their EGA account to an ELIXIR account, allowing the user to access the data via their ELIXIR identity, and hence single sign-on with other cohorts that are compatible with the ELIXIR AAI. In this workflow, the user uses the pyega3 client to transfer data to the data staging area.

1. EGA authenticates the user access. The credentials initially provided by the user when submitting the workflow (ELIXIR AAI Token) are used.
2. If the user does not know to which files or datasets he/she has access to, it is possible to request a list.
3. EGA provides the list of File(s) and Dataset(s).
4. The user requests to download some of the File(s) and/or Dataset(s).
5. EGA starts to download the requested File(s) and/or datasets into the Data staging area.
6. The data downloaded in the previous step is encrypted in transit, but arrives on the local compute environment in a decrypted format.

ENA: Data Access Workflow

¹⁸ <https://github.com/EGA-archive/ega-download-client>

¹⁹ <https://github.com/EGA-archive/ega-fuse-client>

* ENA-Client = FTP, GridFTP, ENA Browser or Aspera clients

Prerequisites: The user must have a supported ENA client (FTP, GridFTP, ENA browser or Aspera clients) installed with access to the Data Staging Area.

1. The user requests for the files she/he wants to download.
2. Files are downloaded to the Data staging area. The user can optionally check the integrity of the files by comparing the MD5 checksum of each of the files.
3. The data downloaded in step 4 is already decrypted format and can be now transferred to the data staging area.

4. Abbreviations

- **AAI**, Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
- **BAM**, Binary Alignment Map
- **CINECA**, Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa
- **CNV**, Copy number variation
- **CoLaus**, study is a population-based cohort of 6734 middle-aged participants from Lausanne (Switzerland)
- **CRAM**, compressed columnar file format for storing biological sequences aligned to a reference sequence
- **CSV**, comma separated data
- **CSC**, IT center for science (Finland)
- **cPouta**, Openstack cloud cluster in CSC
- **CWL**, Common Workflow Language
- **DATS**, Data Tags Suite
- **dbGAP**, database of Genotypes and Phenotypes.
- **DRS**, Data repository service
- **DSA**, Data Staging Area
- **EGA**, European Genome-Phenome Archive.
- **EMBL-EBI**, European Molecular Biology Laboratory, European Bioinformatics Institute
- **ENA**, European Nucleotide Archive
- **eQTL**, Expression quantitative trait locus

- **FASTQ**, text-based format for storing both a biological sequence (usually nucleotide sequence) and its corresponding quality scores. Both the sequence letter and quality score are each encoded with a single ASCII character for brevity.
- **FHIR**, Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
- **FTP**, file transfer protocol
- **GA4GH**, Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
- **GEO**, Gene Expression Omnibus
- **Globus**, open-source toolkit for grid computing
- **GridFTP**, Extension of the File Transfer Protocol (FTP) for grid computing
- **HES-SO**, Haute école spécialisée de Suisse occidentale
- **HRC**, Human Random Control
- **MD5**, Message-digest algorithm, a non-cryptographic hash function
- **PRS**, Polygenic Risk Scores
- **PsyCoLaus** psychiatric subset of CoLaus cohort
- **POC**, Proof Of Concept
- **QTL**, Quantitative trait locus
- **Rahti cloud**, OpenShift OKD Kubernetes cloud cluster in CSC
- **RBAC**, Role-based access control
- **RNA**, Ribonucleic acid
- **SAM**, Sequence Alignment Map
- **SIB**, Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics
- **SNPs**, Single-nucleotide polymorphism
- **SRA**, Sequence Read Archive
- **TES**, Task Execution Service
- **TRS**, Tool repository service
- **VCF**, Variant Call Format
- **WES**, Workflow Execution Service
- **XML**, Extensible Markup Language

5. Work Packages in CINECA

WP1 - Federated Data Discovery and Querying

WP2 - Interoperable Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure

WP3 - Cohort Level Meta Data Representation

WP4 - Federated Joint Cohort Analysis

WP5 - Healthcare Interoperability and Clinical Applications

WP6 - Outreach, training and dissemination

WP7 - Ethical and legal governance framework for transnational data-sharing

WP8 - Project Management and coordination

WP9 - Ethics requirements

6. Delivery and Schedule

The delivery is on time.

7. Appendices

7.1. Data Workflow Survey

The Data Workflow Survey of participating Institutions was carried out in Summer 2019.

Questions

1. What data sources are needed in your analysis workflows?
2. What are the data types you need in your analysis workflows?
3. How is the data ingested into your analysis workflows? What interfaces and protocols do you need for transferring data from data storage to the computing environment?
4. How your analysis workflow authenticates itself to data source & get access to the data?

Answers

HES-SO & SIB

1. CoLaus/PsyCoLaus, EGA
2. Structured clinical data (demographics, diagnosis, prescription); sequences (variants such SNPs, CNV); general research data (pdf, ppt, images, narratives, ...).
3. For meta-data: DATS/DataMed or DCAT. For data: FHIR, csv, ...
4. For EGA, Elixir AAI. For other, Switch AAI (Switzerland)

University of Tartu

1. We use data from various sources. Some of the data are stored locally on the network file system of our high performance computing center, but we also routinely use data from public (European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO)) and controlled access (dbGaP, EGA, Synapse, Google Cloud) repositories.
2. We primarily use three types of data:
 - Genotype data (various file formats that need to be harmonised to a common VCF format before it can be used).
 - RNA sequencing data (mostly in fastq format, dbGAP, GEO and EGA also use other formats (.cram, .bam, .sra).
 - Public references datasets (reference genome sequence, gene annotations, aligner index files, etc)
3. We currently transfer the data manually to our local compute environment, convert to uniform file format (all RNA-seq data to fastq format and all genotype data to VCF format using the same reference genome coordinates). Our computation workflow accesses the data from our local network drive. Automating this in the general case can be challenging due to different access control mechanisms (dbGaP, EGA, Synapse, ad-hoc sFTP sites), file formats (.fastq, .sra, .bam, .cram) and incomplete sample metadata (especially a problem with EGA).
4. The data are first downloaded manually to a local network drive.

University Medical Center Groningen (BIOS)

1. Our data sources are hosted on our local compute cluster. The BIOS data has been generated by multiple Dutch Universities, from their respective biobanks (LifeLines, Leiden Longevity study, Rotterdam Study, Dutch Twin Registry). Public resources are used for follow-up analyses (e.g. interpretation of results), including data from SRA/ENA, GEO, and other datasets.
2. We primarily use three types of data:
 - Genotype data (various file formats that need to be harmonized to a common VCF format before it can be used). Our current software uses an in-house developed representation of these genotypes (TriTyper). Genotype data is generally collected from genotype arrays, and subsequently HRC imputed. If represented as VCF files, they are indexed using tabix.
 - RNA sequencing data (mostly in fastq format), or tab-separated flat text tables containing counts, including all study individuals.
 - Public references datasets (reference genome sequence, gene annotations, aligner index files, etc)
 - Optionally, cell count data (e.g. number of different kinds of white blood cells) and other sample meta-data (e.g. batch, lane, etc) to correct for confounding factors.
3. We currently transfer the data manually to our local compute environment, converting to uniform file format. Our eQTL mapping approach uses the in-house, binary TriTyper format for genotype input, and tab-separated flat text count files as input for RNA-seq data. Our computation workflow accesses the data from our local network drive. No explicit APIs or protocols are currently being employed.
4. Access rights are assigned on a per-user basis on our compute cluster. No access from external parties is available.

University of Oxford

1. Multiple data sources are used some public, some controlled access but most data comes directly from individual cohorts as part of wider consortia efforts
2. Genotype data and phenotype data, in various formats appropriate for the selected analysis programs, usually VCF for genotype data, tab delimited tables for phenotypes
3. Data is manually transferred to the local computing environment. Data transfer both internally and externally usually sftp
4. Data are local to the workflow on the attached file system

University of Cape Town, South Africa

1. Multiple data sources from different H3Africa projects across the continent. The datasets are hosted in institution local machines or clusters. Datasets can also be accessed via access controlled via EGA.
2. Genotype data including both sequence and chip data, phenotype data (demographics, disease status, medication...)
3. Data is ingested manually to computing clusters using sftp and globus online.
4. Data is local to the workflows to authenticated users and. No external access interface available for data access.

European Genome-phenome Archive (EMBL-EBI)

1. Human sequencing data, either exome or whole genome from multiple cohorts
2. Whole genome sequencing aligned to a reference genome. Exome sequencing aligned to a reference genome
3. htsgat for streaming, AAI to gain real-time access
4. This depends on the access protocol of the sources. I imagine that the initial application for access will happen off-line. The workflow would use the provisions in htsgat to authenticate and obtain a token for real-time access.

